

A 5G Roadside Infrastructure Assisting Connected and Automated Vehicles in Vulnerable Road User Protection

RAFFAELE VITERBO¹ (Graduate Student Member, IEEE),
FEDERICO CAMPOLO² (Graduate Student Member, IEEE), MATTIA CERUTTI¹,
SATYESH SHANKER AWASTHI³, STEFANO ARRIGONI³, MATTIA BRAMBILLA¹ (Member, IEEE),
AND MONICA NICOLI⁴ (Senior Member, IEEE)

¹Dipartimento di Elettronica, Informazione e Bioingegneria, Politecnico di Milano, 20133 Milan, Italy

²AI-Driven Systems, i2CAT Foundation, 08034 Barcelona, Spain

³Dipartimento di Meccanica, Politecnico di Milano, 20133 Milan, Italy

⁴Dipartimento di Ingegneria Gestionale, Politecnico di Milano, 20133 Milan, Italy

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: R. VITERBO (e-mail: raffaele.viterbo@polimi.it)

This work was supported in part by the funding program POR-FESR 2014-2020 Project BASE5G (Broadband Interfaces and Services for Smart Environments enabled by 5G technologies) under Grant 1155850; in part by the European Union—NextGenerationEU under the National Sustainable Mobility Center under Grant CN0000023; and in part by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR) under Grant 1033—17/06/2022 (Spoke 6).

ABSTRACT Road safety is one of the major concerns when considering road vehicles, with issues referring to both drivers and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) (e.g., pedestrians). The role of roadside infrastructures in augmenting VRU protection is gaining popularity thanks to the development of smart and connected sensing systems, which enable the detection of critical events and their forwarding to nearby Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) by Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications. In this context, the fifth generation (5G) of mobile radio networks is emerging as the communication enabler for advanced V2X services for CAVs. In this work we propose the design, development, and assessment on road of a 5G roadside infrastructure for VRU protection, performing an in-depth analysis of the single components and their integration into the service. More specifically, we present a Roadside Unit (RSU) capable to detect, localize, and track VRUs; a communication architecture that exploits 5G V2X connectivity for sending VRUs detections; a CAV with on-board algorithms warning the driver of the presence of the VRU and an Autonomous Emergency Braking (AEB) solution triggered by the 5G V2X architecture. We validate the efficacy of the proposed solution in a road scenario inside the campus of Politecnico di Milano.

INDEX TERMS 5G mobile communication, autonomous emergency braking, connected mobility, localization, pedestrians, road safety, roadside infrastructure, vehicular automation, vehicular technologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

SMART roads rely on intelligent infrastructures that integrate sensing, computing, and communication technologies to improve traffic safety, efficiency and sustainability or road mobility, by the implementation of Cooperative Intelligent Transport System (C-ITS) [1]. Sensing is performed by devices like cameras, radars, Light

Detection And Ranging (LiDAR), or ultrasonic [2], [3]. Collected information refers to roadside (e.g., vehicle type/weight), wide-area (e.g., video analysis or satellite acquisitions from space), or floating car data (e.g., Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)) [4]. Computing abilities reside in ad-hoc hardware (edge intelligence) or cloud facilities (edge cloud) through Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC), ensuring low latency for analytics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) [5]. Communication links exploit

The review of this article was arranged by Associate Editor Jiaqi Ma.

Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) technology (such as Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) [6], [7]) either based on Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN), like the American Dedicated Short-Range Communication (DSRC) and its European counterpart ITS-G5, or on the 4th Generation (4G), 5th Generation (5G) and future 6th Generation (6G) cellular networks [8], referred as Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X). Both technologies operate in the regulated 5.9-GHz band [9], [10] and they have been tested in real-life environments [11], [12]. The cellular technology could also be used for positioning services [13], [14], [15].

Roadside Units (RSUs) and infrastructure-based platforms of a smart road can provide C-ITS services to road users through V2X communications. Day-1 use cases specified by the 5G Automotive Association (5GAA) in [16], along with their spectrum needs, can be implemented by leveraging the RSU edge intelligence; examples are intersection movement assistance, emergency brake warning, traffic jam warning, lane change warning, or automated intersection crossing. The role of the RSU is also essential for future deployments of services for Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) [17]. In this context, the RSU is able to provide trusted assistance data for road safety [18] and high-quality traffic information for autonomous driving tasks [19], [20], thus augmenting CAVs' awareness on-board services such as cooperative perception [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], cooperative maneuvering [26], [27], highly-directional communications [28], [29], [30], edge computing [31], [32], and dedicated networking protocols [33], [34].

While we acknowledge the uptake of CAV technologies and related services, guaranteeing the protection of Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) is an overriding key requirement for safe mobility. Toward this end, an RSU edge intelligence able to detect, localize and track VRUs represents a pivotal element that can be deployed already as day-1 service for monitoring an area of interest and alerting vehicles in proximity, as well as for characterizing pedestrian flows [35]. Machine Learning (ML) methodologies for 3D object detection are increasingly important [36] for autonomous driving applications [37]. Pedestrian detection based on a fine-tuned Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) can outperform traditional methods that use handcrafted features (i.e., the feature extraction pipeline is the result of human intuition and understanding of the raw data), providing an accuracy close to that of state-of-the-art approaches (e.g., AlexNet [38], GoogLeNet [39]) while requiring a low computational [40] and communication [41] time.

Examples of VRUs protection solutions can be found in the literature [42], [43]. Specifically, in [42], the authors propose an in-vehicle system for detecting and tracking pedestrians using vehicle-mounted cameras, however their system does not consider detailed information such as pedestrians' velocity or angle. The work carried out in [43] aims at improving VRU detection performance in dark

environments by using thermal images along with video, still the miss rate is as high as 14% owing to the Line-of-Sight (LOS) requirement. Experimental assessments for VRU protection can be found in [44], [45], dealing with urban scenarios: therein, in the context of a large-scale roadside infrastructure, a pedestrian receives a notification about an imminent hazard on a smartphone and the vehicle is also notified through its On-Board Unit (OBU). Yet, no automatic mechanism is implemented to slow down or stop the vehicle based on hazard's proximity. Another experimentation is detailed in [46], where a description of an RSU is provided for vehicle localization at an urban intersection.

Together with the technological advancement of the RSUs, in recent years we have been witnessing a major improvement in vehicle on-board sensing and computation technologies. The global Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) market is estimated to reach approximately a value of \$158 billion by 2032, expanding at a growth rate of 13.80% per annum [47]. Among the different systems encompassed under ADAS, the active safety system of Autonomous Emergency Braking (AEB) is a key for reducing the number of accidents by 22-30% [48]. AEB is a system designed to detect potential collisions and automatically brake to prevent or mitigate the impact. These systems typically rely on calculating the Time to Collision (TTC) as a parameter for determining the risk of collision. Studies have shown that in certain situations, human drivers underestimate the risk, making AEB systems valuable in improving safety through sensor-based estimations [49]. A main limit in current systems is that the sensor-based configuration may lead to errors during adverse weather conditions [50] or when certain parameters, such as road grip or occlusions, are not considered [51].

Improvements in collision avoidance systems can be obtained via V2X communications, which allow the vehicles and VRUs to be notified of their mutual presence along with additional information about their state, also known as Cooperative Collision Avoidance (CCA). The work in [52] studies the safety improvements for an intersection scenario with a vehicle and a bicycle. Other examples, instead, use V2X communications for predicting the collision with a pedestrian [53], [54], [55], [56]. Infrastructure-side awareness represents a paradigm shift in this context: here, the RSU is primarily responsible for VRU detection and tracking by means of a suitable perception system, and this information can be encoded into a Collaborative Perception Message (CPM) transmitted over the V2X network [57].

The state-of-the-art literature on VRU protection emphasizes the absence of comprehensive analyses and experimental evaluations of overall system performance, encompassing all components from sensing to control. It also highlights the need for an analysis of latency impacts, including communication and actuation performance, as well as the development and evaluation of edge intelligence to extract pedestrian-specific parameters and an automated

mechanism, activated via V2X communication, to bring the vehicle to a stop. To address these shortcomings, in this work we design, develop, and assess a C-ITS architecture for VRU protection in a real urban environment. Our proposed solution differentiates from the others by providing a complete system description, not prioritizing single elements or methodologies. In addition, we propose an edge intelligence algorithm running on the RSU to extract pedestrian-specific parameters, namely velocity, direction heading, latitude, and longitude. A further contribution is related to the automatic triggering of AEB via 5G communication link, based on the parameters extracted by the RSU. The proposed C-ITS solution includes (i) an RSU method for detection, localization, and tracking of VRU, (ii) a V2X communication architecture based on 5G technology, and (iii) an on-board vehicle intelligence triggering and actuating the AEB according to the information received from the infrastructure by 5G. Specific contributions are as follows:

- *Integrated V2X communication and actuation system:* we develop a V2X communication architecture leveraging 5G connectivity and a custom message encoding to transmit localization data from the RSU to OBU of a CAV, enhancing its environmental awareness and improving safety in mobility. This architecture supports an on-board pedestrian-intersection collision warning and avoidance system that alerts drivers of the VRU presence and autonomously triggers the AEB if warnings are ignored, enabling seamless automated braking through the integrated communication framework;
- *On-field demonstration and assessment:* we conduct an on-field demonstration in an urban scenario at Politecnico di Milano campus, involving a CAV approaching a limited-visibility turn near a zebra crossing while analyzing C-ITS performance metrics such as pedestrian positioning error, V2X message latency, stability, reliability, security, and the vehicle's braking and remaining distances from the VRU.

This paper is structured as follows: Section II provides an overview of the different architectural components of our solution, namely smart RSU, V2X communication system, and on-board intelligence, along with their functionalities and how they interact among each other; Section III is devoted to explain the experimental setup as well as the hardware details of our C-ITS solution; Section IV summarizes the main obtained numerical results; Section V concludes the work.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND METHODOLOGY

This section presents the proposed architecture for the VRU protection system, along with the main components represented by the smart RSU (for VRU detection, tracking, and localization), the V2X communication system and the control engine at the CAV, as summarized in Fig. 1. Their functionalities are described in the following, also specifying how they interact among each other.

FIGURE 1. System architecture highlighting the three designed components: smart RSU, V2X communication, and on-board intelligence.

A. SMART RSU

The goal of a smart RSU is to sense the vehicular scene in a predefined area (e.g., a pedestrian crossing), detect and estimate the position, velocity, and direction of a VRU. Towards this end, a technique combining object recognition with Kalman filter tracking is employed, allowing us to estimate the CAV speed, direction, and position in the 3D space of a pedestrian from a 2D optical image. We leverage a Computer Vision (CV) algorithm running on camera frames for VRU detection and tracking, which extracts pedestrian-specific parameters. RSU connectivity is provided by a mobile 5G hotspot network, which allows to share data with CAVs. The proposed smart RSU architecture integrates two distinct parts, namely sensing and edge intelligence, as detailed in the following.

Regarding sensing, the designated area is monitored by a camera operating in the visible electromagnetic spectrum. The camera is attached to the edge intelligence via USB connection, and the observed scene is retrieved by a software script. On the other hand, the edge intelligence is an embedded computer running the detection, tracking, and localization algorithms. Once all the VRU's related parameters are extracted, the edge intelligence sends the data to the CAV by means of the V2X communication channel as depicted in Fig. 1.

For real-time detection of pedestrians we rely on You Only Look Once v4 (YOLOv4), a single-shot detector model based on CNN that makes use of bag of freebies techniques [58] to improve the training accuracy without increasing the cost of inference. While the detection step produces a set of Bounding Boxes (BBs) for the current frame, the tracking module associates such detections over time to improve the localization accuracy. For this purpose, we consider the Deep Neural Network (DNN) model DeepSORT [59], based on the Simple Online and Realtime Tracking (SORT) algorithm for Multi-Object Tracking (MOT). Basic SORT applies a Kalman filter in the image space and a frame-by-frame data association based on the Hungarian method. However, this approach leads to a relatively high number of identity switches, because the employed association metric is only accurate when state estimation uncertainty is low (e.g., when there are no occlusions). To cope with this problem, we employ the association rule in [59] which

FIGURE 2. Bird's eye view image transformation of the considered ROI. Left: camera image space. Right: ground image space as a result of ROI projection.

combines motion and appearance information by applying a CNN trained to discriminate pedestrians on a large scale person re-identification dataset. We observed that this leads to a reduction of identity switches by 45%, improving basic SORT performances.

The VRU localization algorithm aims at detecting and tracking VRUs from camera images. The detections are provided in terms of BBs in the camera image space, defined by the coordinate space (u, v) , while the absolute VRU positions are referred to a universal coordinate system (e.g., Latitude Longitude Altitude (LLA)). The conversion from local to global coordinates involves the projection on the ground floor, defined by the coordinates (x, y) , which are referred to as ground image space. Fig. 2 shows an example of this transformation used to localize the VRUs.

For each camera frame f , the localization algorithm entails the following steps. First, each detected BB i , $i = 1, \dots, N_{BB}$, is associated to the ground point in the camera image space corresponding to the orthogonal projection of the BB center. Then, a Bird's Eye View (BEV) transformation [60] is performed to project all the points within a Region Of Interest (ROI) of the camera image space from the camera coordinates (u, v) to the ground image space (x, y) . This projection allows finding the ground points in ground coordinates, which are then converted from local coordinates into the LLA global coordinates. The algorithm also returns an estimate of the speed and direction of the detected BBs, saving the information in a pickle file that is sent to the CAV over the V2X link.

The required process for calibrating the camera detections and converting the reference systems of coordinates is described in the Appendix. Once the calibration is completed, the algorithm starts following the localization and tracking pipeline as follows: first it performs the detection of the i -th VRU at frame f and starts tracking it across the next frames. The detection produces a set of coordinates for the corresponding BB in the image space. Then, the algorithm proceeds to the localization step where it projects the image space into the BEV space (e.g., the real horizontal space),

and determines the i -th BB coordinates in this new space. These new coordinates of the i -th BB in the horizontal space correspond to the estimated location for the i -th detected VRU at frame f .

B. V2X COMMUNICATION SYSTEM

The V2X communication system enables the message exchange between RSU CAV. It accounts for two aspects: a communication protocol at the application layer, and a software script capable to manage the connection to such protocol in order to send/receive messages. We provide further details in the following.

1) COMMUNICATION PROTOCOL

We develop a connector based on the Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) communication protocol. MQTT defines two types of network entities: a message broker and a number of clients. The former is a server that receives all messages from the clients and then routes them to the destination, the latter are devices running an MQTT library and connecting to the broker over the network. In the MQTT protocol, the exchanged messages are identified, filtered and routed according to a topic: publishers send messages about specific topics, and subscribers receive the messages by subscribing to those topics. The main features of MQTT are as follows:

- *Lightweight and efficient*: MQTT clients are very small and require minimal resources;
- *Reliable message delivery*: ensuring of different levels of reliability is possible in MQTT by specifying Quality of Service (QoS) levels (0, 1, and 2);
- *Security enabled*: encryption of messages is possible by Transport Layer Security (TLS) and client authentication via Open Authorization (OAuth);
- *Communication flexibility*: the broker relies on topics to determine which clients receive specific messages, decoupling the sender and the receiver.

FIGURE 3. Schemes for latency computation. (a) Single publisher and subscriber. (b) Devices act as publisher and subscriber at the same time.

The broker (hence the V2X communication system) can be a common laptop, an edge computer, or even a fully-fledged server, and it can be deployed either on-premise or cloud.

2) SOFTWARE FOR MESSAGE EXCHANGE

A Python script is employed to handle the message exchange and the connection to the broker by the clients. More specifically, we exploit the Paho MQTT library [61] providing a client class with support for MQTT v5.0, v3.1.1, and v3.1. It is noteworthy to point out two features of the Paho MQTT library, that are:

- *Callback functions*: 7 callbacks are associated to as many events (i.e., connection, disconnection, subscription, unsubscription, message publish, message reception, log availability);
- *Loop functions*: when called, the client class processes network events at regular intervals (e.g., forwarding published messages, subscription to a topic, incoming messages reception, etc.).

The scripts run on both the embedded computer (smart RSU) and a common laptop emulating the CAV's OBU. We considered two metrics to assess the broker implementation performance, namely average latency and stability of the communication channel. For their computations we refer to the schemes in Fig. 3, where we represent the path the message follows from the sender to the receiver. Each client publishes a message on a certain topic and subscribes either to the same (Fig. 3(a)) or to a different one (Fig. 3(b)), with the broker in charge of routing the message on the correct topic. Variables t_{TX} and t_{RX} indicate the timestamps a message is sent and received, respectively. The variables involved in the latency computations are the following:

- τ_f : it is the time the message takes to reach the machine hosting the MQTT broker, including the propagation time of the electromagnetic waves and the transmission

time along the communication channel, depending on the available bandwidth, number of hops, network congestion and switching latency;

- τ_{proc} : it is the processing time the MQTT broker takes to process the incoming packet.

We compute the delay as Round Trip Time (RTT) in order to avoid any clock phase bias between sender and receiver. For the k -th exchanged message the RTT is given by $\tau_k = (t_{RX,k} - t_{TX,k})/2$, where $t_{RX,k}$ is the time instant message k was received and $t_{TX,k}$ is the time instant message k was sent. This leads to the computation of the average V2X communication latency μ and stability σ_k respectively as

$$\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \tau_k, \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_k = \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[(\tau_k - \mu)^2]}. \quad (2)$$

C. PROTOTYPE VEHICLE

Vehicle connectivity is enabled thanks to a 5G mobile hotspot connected to the OBU. The incoming data from the camera must be properly interpreted and processed by the OBU of the CAV. For this purpose, we resort to Robot Operating System (ROS) [62], a set of software libraries and tools that enables motors, sensors, software, and batteries to work all together seamlessly, performing a given task. One of ROS's main strengths is its direct action upon the mechanical parts of the vehicle, for instance braking system, steering system, etc., thanks to a Controller Area Network (CAN) bus interface. Similar to MQTT, ROS utilizes a publish/subscribe paradigm, but messages require a very specific syntax in order to be correctly decoded. We define a custom format of a ROS message, as reported in Fig. 4. The field `data` is a ROS keyword that can store an array of values. In

```

{
  "data": [
    {
      "id": 0,
      "velocity": 26.3599,
      "direction": 0,
      "latitude": 45.7749,
      "longitude": 9.4194
    },
    {
      "id": 1,
      "velocity": 6.3241,
      "direction": 30,
      "latitude": 15.9024,
      "longitude": 21.5117
    },
    :
  ]
}

```

FIGURE 4. Example of a ROS-compatible message.

every position there is a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)-formatted message containing the fields *ID* (unsigned 8-bit integer), *Velocity* (64-bit IEEE float), *Direction* (unsigned 16-bit integer), *Latitude* (64-bit IEEE float), and *Longitude* (64-bit IEEE float). The values of the variables in the message are given as output of the detection and tracking algorithms. Along with the message described above coming from the RSU, which is then converted into a ROS message locally, the OBU also subscribes to the information published by on-board sensors and the map data. These act as an input for the Simulink-based Collision Warning and Avoidance System (CWAS) algorithm. The algorithm publishes warning and AEB trigger messages on the ROS network for the Human Machine Interface (HMI) and the AEB actuation system, respectively.

The control logic flow of the developed CWAS algorithm is shown in Fig. 5. It includes the following sub-modules:

- *State estimation*: it uses an Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) based on single track kinematic model to estimate velocities, heading angle and positioning of the vehicle in real-time. It uses the data from on-board GNSS, magnetic speed sensors of the two rear tone wheels and incremental optical encoder connected to the DC motor of the electronic power steering system of the vehicle. A description of the algorithm is in [63].
- *VRU collision detection*: it receives an input from the map data block, state estimator and ROS network and outputs the value of TTC;
- *Collision warning and braking decision*: it consists of two parts, one that decides whether to warn or not and another that makes the braking decision based on the TTC value received as input;
- *Brake actuation*: it generates a ROS message, calibrated to the braking system, to deliver the needed braking pressure for the requested deceleration.

The two key parameters used in the algorithm are Time To Reach (TTR) and TTC. TTR is the real-time estimate of the time the vehicle would need to reach the current position of the detected VRU, based on the vehicle's and VRU's relative

position and velocity. The TTC parameter, instead, indicates the threshold value for the activation of AEB to successfully avoid collision. It accounts for an average braking response time of the actuation system and a desired safe clearance distance between the vehicle and the VRU after the braking maneuver is completed. The TTC values for a range of vehicle speeds are pre-calculated and compared with the TTR in real-time. When TTR exceeds TTC, the AEB is activated. In this work, the TTC calculated as described above is named as TTC_2 , while $TTC_1 = TTC_2 + 2\text{ s}$. When TTR crosses TTC_1 , a warning for the driver is activated to manually intervene 2 s before the critical value is reached. The details of the calculation of TTR and TTC are presented in the following paragraphs, respectively.

The position inputs obtained from the state estimation block using the GNSS measurements are converted from UTM coordinate system to local curvilinear (s , y) road coordinate system using the data from the map of the road. The s -coordinate represents the distance along the road while the y -coordinate signifies the distance along the road width.

The positions of the road center-line, the ego vehicle and the VRU during one of the experimental runs in the three coordinate systems are shown in Fig. 7. TTR and TTC are standard metrics, however, these values change with the different methods of calculation of distance between the agents involved. The previous works calculate the relative distances in Cartesian co-ordinates and limit themselves to straight line trajectories [51], [64]. All the calculations in the CWAS algorithm developed in this work have been performed in s - y coordinates because it aligns with the natural structure of the movement of the vehicle along a path and decouples the longitudinal and the lateral displacement along that path. Using this coordinate system, curved trajectories along real roads can be accounted without complex calculations at each time step. Moreover, the assumption that the vehicle follows the center-line trajectory also represents the condition capable of generating the lowest possible TTC value, thereby representing the condition of maximum danger. The collision detection block initially performs the checks on the input states of the vehicle and the VRU. If the vehicle is moving and a VRU has been detected by the RSU, the algorithm proceeds with TTR calculation based on the position along the road length (s coordinate) adjusted for by the vehicle length and the safety zone, otherwise it outputs an arbitrary value (high) for the same. The calculations for the TTR are as follows

$$\Delta s = s_{\text{VRU}} - s_v, \quad (3)$$

$$TTR = \begin{cases} -\frac{\Delta s}{v_{r,s}}, & \forall v_{r,s} < 0, a_{r,s} = 0, \\ -\frac{v_{r,s} - \sqrt{v_{r,s}^2 - 2\Delta s \cdot a_{r,s}}}{a_{r,s}}, & \forall v_{r,s} < 0, a_{r,s} \neq 0, \\ -\frac{v_{r,s} + \sqrt{v_{r,s}^2 - 2\Delta s \cdot a_{r,s}}}{a_{r,s}}, & \forall v_{r,s} \geq 0, a_{r,s} \neq 0, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

FIGURE 5. Flowchart of the control logic among the different modules of the CWAS algorithm.

where s_{VRU} and s_v are the s -coordinates position of VRU and vehicle, respectively, and $v_{r,s}$ and $a_{r,s}$ are the velocity and acceleration of the vehicle with respect to the VRU, respectively along the road center-line. TTR cannot be calculated for $v_{r,s}, a_{r,s} \geq 0$, as the relative distance between the VRU and the vehicle does not decrease, and for $v_{r,s}^2 - 2\Delta s \cdot a_{r,s} < 0$. It is to be noted that s_v in (3) is the s -coordinate of the front end of the vehicle. The calculated TTR is used for predicting the VRU position along the y -coordinate thanks to the decoupling of the lateral and the longitudinal displacement along the path in curvilinear coordinates. It is assumed that the VRU travels at a constant speed and in the direction provided in the message from the RSU. Based on the calculated TTR, the future position of VRU is calculated as

$$y_{VRU}(TTR) = y_{VRU}(t) + v_{VRU,y} \cdot TTR, \quad (5)$$

where y_{VRU} is the y position of the VRU and $v_{VRU,y}$ is the velocity of the VRU in y direction. This position is updated each time a new message on the state of the VRUs is received from the RSU. A critical zone is predicted in the y direction along the crosswalk. The critical zone consist of the point $[y_v(TTR) - 0.5w - w_{sz}, y_v + 0.5w + y_{sz}]$, where y_v is the position of vehicle along the y coordinate, w is the width of the vehicle and w_{sz} is the width of the safety zone around the vehicle. $y_v(TTR)$ can be calculated from velocity and acceleration of the vehicle. If the VRU is calculated to be within the critical zone when the vehicle reaches the intersection (Fig. 6), the collision warning and braking decision sub-module proceeds with the comparison between the TTR and the TTCs. Further actions are decided by the block based on the rules embedded in the brake actuation sub-module. It is to be noted that the action taken is based on the minimum value of TTR obtained when multiple VRUs are present.

FIGURE 6. Visual representation of the critical zone for an arbitrary VRU and ego vehicle state (opaque yellow car). It is the red zone along the road width where the collision probability is maximum if vehicle brakes are not engaged.

FIGURE 7. The map and positions of the ego vehicle and the VRU represented in three coordinate systems. The GNSS estimates received as latitude and longitude geographical information are first converted into UTM global Cartesian coordinates and subsequently into local s - y coordinates.

TTC calculation is a critical part of any AEB algorithm and it must account for the total braking distance, which consists in *actuator response distance*, *braking distance*, and

FIGURE 8. The total braking distance for TTC calculation is composed of a minimum safe distance which depends on the braking system characteristics and a chosen safety distance.

FIGURE 9. (a) Total braking distance as per deceleration profile vs velocity; (b) TTC vs velocity.

safety distance (Fig. 8). The actuator response distance is the distance traveled by the vehicle in the time interval from when the braking action is initiated to when the desired deceleration is achieved. The braking distance is the distance travelled by the vehicle at the desired acceleration request. In this work, the following sequential AEB deceleration logic was implemented based on the vehicle velocity input:

- if $v_v \leq 30$ km/h, $a_{req} = -10$ m/s²,
- if 30 km/h $\leq v_v \leq 50$ km/h, $a_{req} = -3.5$ m/s² for 300 ms, followed by $a_{req} = -6$ m/s²,
- if $v_v \geq 50$ km/h, $a_{req} = -3.5$ m/s²,

The safety distance adds additional redundancy to the system, avoiding to brake too close to VRUs and startling them causing panic situations. It also compensates for inaccuracies that may occur in sensing, assumptions and variation in vehicle dynamics due to change in environmental and temporal factors. TTC_2 in Fig. 5 indicates that for a TTR value less than TTC_2 , the vehicle will reach the desired position before it can come to a complete stop. Fig. 9(a) shows the total braking distance and Fig. 9(b) the TTC for different vehicle velocities based on the logic stated above.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, we provide the details of our experimental assessment carried out in the Durando Campus of Politecnico di Milano (Fig. 10(a)), including the hardware of the smart RSU (Figs. 10(b)-10(c)) and the CAV (Fig. 10(d)). In the designated site, a CAV approaches a limited-visibility turn behind which a pedestrian crossing is present.

A. SMART RSU SPECIFICATIONS

The role of the embedded PC is taken by the NVIDIA[®] Jetson[™] Xavier NX Developer Kit board, which exploits the JetPack Software Development Kit (SDK) release 4.5 including a custom Ubuntu 18.04 OS based on the NVIDIA[®]

TABLE 1. Specifications of the embedded PC and camera.

Component	Details
NVIDIA [®] Jetson [™] Xavier NX Developer Kit	21 TOPS
	384-core NVIDIA Volta architecture [™] GPU with 48 tensor Cores
	1100 MHz GPU maximum frequency
	6-core NVIDIA Carmel Arm v8.2 [®] 64-bit CPU 6MB L2 + 4 MB L3
	8 GB of LPDDR4x RAM
	1.9 GHz CPU maximum frequency
Camera	720 × 540 resolution
	0.4 megapixels
	522 maximum FPS
	Sony IMX287 sensor
	USB 3.1 Gen 1 interface
	Visible spectrum

Jetson[™] Linux for Tegra (L4T) 32.5. Thanks to its characteristics, the board is well suited to run both YOLOv4 and DeepSORT algorithms for accurate detection and tracking of pedestrians. The camera is provided by Teledyne FLIR and it is a Blackfly S USB3 model. The main specifications of the two elements are in Table 1.

B. CAV SPECIFICATIONS

The test vehicle is an electric ZhiDou model (Fig. 10(d)) with its OBU running autonomous driving algorithms. It hosts the ROS network and connects to a CAN network via an Electronic Control Unit (ECU) (Fig. 10(f)), which also links to the AEB actuator, speed sensors and steering encoder. It is the same model as the one described in [65] in terms of dimensions, power transmission and mechanical parameters like mass and inertia. However, the brake actuation system has been modified for our specific use case. In particular, it comprises a piston (Fig. 10(e)) that provides input to the brake pedal based on the output of CWAS. For the experimental tests, the higher brake acceleration commands, as discussed in Section II-C, have been truncated at -6 m/s². The truncation was needed to maintain the integrity of the brake pedal actuator under high frequency applications, where the magnitude of braking is limited mechanically. This results in a change (increase) in both the TTC parameter and braking distance for vehicle velocities lower than 50 km/h as shown in Fig. 9(b).

The OBU has a GNSS receiver with antenna mounted on the roof, and it receives the Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) corrections from a fixed base station. An HMI module receives the ROS messages containing vehicle position, velocity and TTC information based on the calculations on the OBU. It then converts such information into graphical

FIGURE 10. (a) Top view of the experimental area. RSU hardware: (b) NVIDIA® embedded PC. (c) FLIR camera. (d) Test vehicle. Systems on the autonomous vehicle: (e) CAN ECU (f) AEB actuator (g) HMI.

data on the screen to be easily interpreted on-board, as shown in Fig. 10(g).

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents the achieved results for the localization algorithm at the RSU (Section IV-A), the V2X communication systems connecting the RSU and the CAV (Section IV-B), and the on-board vehicle algorithm for AEB (Section II-C). The localization algorithm is assessed in terms of localization accuracy, inference time and Frames Per Second (FPS). The V2X communication system is evaluated considering the latency and the stability of the message exchange. The overall AEB performance is evaluated in terms of the braking distance and safety distance.

A. LOCALIZATION ALGORITHM AT RSU

During the experimental assessment, the performance of the proposed VRU localization algorithm is evaluated in terms of localization accuracy and inference time. We define a ROI of $6 \times 8 \text{ m}^2$ (Fig. 2), further divided into squares of $2 \times 2 \text{ m}^2$. In this way, we identify a set of $N_{GT} = 20$ ground truth points (Fig. 11) that we use to conduct our tests. Each performance metric is benchmarked over a 10 s video, one per each ground truth position. During these videos, one VRU is standing still right on top of the ground truth position, while around and in the background other VRUs are passing by. Each video is recorded via a 2018 iPad Pro

FIGURE 11. Grid visualization of the ground truth points in the ROI.

having a 12 MP camera recording at 1080p, 30 FPS. The iPad is placed over a tripod at a height of 1.8 m, with a distance of approximately 3 m from the bottom-right corner of the ROI and an orientation of 70° towards the ROI. This setup has been chosen to allow the limited Field Of View (FOV) of the camera to include the whole area of the ROI.

The localization accuracy is evaluated in terms of Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), by testing the algorithm over the set of N_{GT} ground truth points depicted in Fig. 11. To do so, we feed the inference videos to the localization system,

FIGURE 12. Results of VRU localization algorithm over the ROI ground truth positions. (a) Positioning RMSE heatmap for YOLOv4. (b) Positioning RMSE heatmap for YOLOv4-tiny. (c) Positioning RMSE heatmap for YOLOv11n. (d) Inference time for YOLOv4. (e) Inference time for YOLOv4-tiny. (f) Inference time for YOLOv11n.

which returns a position estimation of the VRU at each video frame f . The RMSE over the 10 s videos of each reference point $P_{GT}^{(j)}$, $j = 1, \dots, N_{GT}$, is calculated as

$$RMSE^{(j)} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{f=1}^F (\hat{P}_{GT,f}^{(j)} - P_{GT}^{(j)})^2}{F}}, \quad (6)$$

with F being the total number of frames, and $\hat{P}_{GT,f}^{(j)}$ and $P_{GT}^{(j)}$ the estimated and true j -th position at frame f , respectively.

We compare the YOLOv4 and YOLOv4-tiny detection algorithms also in terms of their inference time, computed as the amount of time taken by the system to analyze a camera frame. This metric allows to determine the suitability of a model given the specific application requirements. The objective is to develop a system working in real time with a frame rate of at least 10 FPS [66], which corresponds to a latency lower than 100 ms. We consider both detection only and detection plus tracking performances. The inference time is then averaged over the 10 s videos of each ground truth point and is evaluated also in terms of FPS.

Figs. 12(a) and 12(b) report the positioning RMSE over the ROI of the VRU localization algorithm using YOLOv4 and YOLOv4-tiny, respectively. In both cases we observe a degradation from the bottom-right corner towards the top-left one. This behavior is explained by a decrease in resolution of the BEV projected image of the ROI. Recall that the camera is close to the bottom-right corner of the ROI. As a result, the projection of the camera image into the ground image causes a distortion in the density of pixel per meter. This can be appreciated in Fig. 11, where the

ground image shows a higher resolution around $P_{GT}^{(20)}$ rather than $P_{GT}^{(1)}$. For this reason, the error of a pixel close to the bottom-right corner of the ROI results in a smaller error in meters as compared to an error of one pixel in the top-left corner, after projection in the ground image. This result highlights the significant difference in detection accuracy between YOLOv4 and YOLOv4-tiny: while using the first one leads to an average RMSE over the ROI of 14.7 cm, the scaled model leads to an average RMSE of 23.9 cm.

Figs. 12(d) and 12(e) report the inference time of the VRU localization system, averaged over the 10 s recording. The two plots refer to both latency for detection only and detection plus tracking, and the performance is evaluated in both ms (top) and FPS (bottom). Once again we observe a clear performance difference between the two models, with YOLOv4-tiny having shorter inference times and higher FPSs compared to YOLOv4. Still, both models have a sufficiently low latency when performing detection only, with the YOLOv4 model showing an average inference time of 8 ms, against the 2 ms of the scaled model. The introduction of the tracking task has a meaningful impact on the overall latency of the system, increasing the average inference time by an order of magnitude (from 8 to 80 ms for the YOLOv4 model, and from 2 to 20 ms for the scaled one). Nonetheless, in both cases the system meets the 100 ms maximum latency objective of the application.

The last assessment of the localization algorithm at the RSU aims to compare the performance of YOLOv4 and YOLOv4-tiny models with the latest state of the art model YOLOv11n. The choice of YOLOv11n is motivated by its specific purpose of being oriented to applications on

edge devices that require real-time performances, as is our case. The differences in localization performance between YOLOv4, YOLOv4-tiny, and YOLOv11n can be attributed to their architectural and computational improvements. Specifically, YOLOv11n incorporates advanced feature extraction techniques and enhanced multi-scale detection mechanisms, which enable superior accuracy, particularly for small or partially occluded objects [67]. Compared to YOLOv4 and YOLOv4-tiny which have approximately 64 and 6 million parameters, YOLOv11n benefits from a deeper and more optimized architecture with 8 million parameters, leading to more precise bounding box predictions and, consequently, reduced localization errors. However, these improvements come at the expense of computational cost, resulting in increased inference time. Figs. 12(c) and 12(f) show the performance of YOLOv11n over the test set. In particular, YOLOv11n achieves the best RMSE of approximately 10 cm, corresponding to a gain of about 30% compared to YOLOv4 and about 58% compared to YOLOv4-tiny. Conversely, the inference time ranges between $4 \cdot 10^2$ and $7 \cdot 10^2$, ms, which corresponds to 18 and 25 FPS. While YOLOv11n offers similar inference times compared to YOLOv4 when performing both detection and tracking, it is almost 80% slower than YOLOv4-tiny in the Detection + Tracking case and 90% slower in the Detection-only case.

These results highlight the importance of a trade-off in the RSU design and implementation, offering the opportunity to adapt it according to the application requirements. While the use of the YOLOv11n model leads to the best localization accuracy as well as the capacity of detecting and tracking many VRUs at the same time, it necessitates higher inference times. On the other hand, by slightly sacrificing the accuracy performance and the capacity of detecting and tracking many VRUs, the scaled YOLOv4-tiny model is capable of delivering a quick response, even with non-complex hardware such as the one considered. This aspect plays an important role in the protection of VRUs, since a smaller latency gives more time to react in case of an emergency situation.

B. V2X COMMUNICATION SYSTEM

A human driver undergoes different phases when a hazard appears on the road. These can be identified as *hazard perception*, *reaction to hazard*, and *braking*. According to [68], the first two account for a time that goes from 0.6 s up to 1.5 s. Braking is intended as the time it takes to move the foot from the accelerator to the brake pedal, and according to [69] the most important variable affecting braking is driver expectation. Specifically:

- Braking to known signals takes from 0.7 s to 0.75 s,
- Braking to unexpected, but common, signals takes about 1.25 s,
- Braking to surprise events takes roughly 1.5 s.

TABLE 2. Summary results for V2X latency.

	Type of connection	Broker	Average latency [ms]	
One device	Ethernet	test.mosquitto.org	118.1	
		VPN with ngrok	External Mosquitto	708.5
			Localhost Mosquitto	211.4
		IBM Watson IoT Platform	46.4	
	Two devices	WiFi	test.mosquitto.org	154.7
			VPN with ngrok	External Mosquitto
Localhost Mosquitto				240
		IBM Watson IoT Platform	47.2	
Two devices		Ethernet	test.mosquitto.org	527.7
	VPN with ngrok		External Mosquitto	456.8
			Localhost Mosquitto	N/A
		IBM Watson IoT Platform	46.38	
	Two devices	WiFi	test.mosquitto.org	484.3
			VPN with ngrok	External Mosquitto
Localhost Mosquitto				N/A
		IBM Watson IoT Platform	48.83	
	Shared	Mosquitto	104.5	

For our practical purposes, we consider the benchmark of tolerated V2X communication latency to be 600 ms. Despite being much higher compared to the safety requirements of automated driving, the goal of our smart RSU is to augment CAV's reaction to hazards by tackling the most critical phase of hazard perception. If the information to CAV were to take more than the human perception benchmark of 600 ms, our VRU protection scenario could not be ensured and thus our smart RSU would not be deemed safer compared to manual driving.

Table 2 summarizes the obtained results, analyzing both different communication settings (one/two devices with a wired/wireless/shared connection) and MQTT broker implementations (local/cloud). The considered brokers are:

- *test.mosquitto.org*: the publicly available cloud version of the Mosquitto broker. A local implementation on a PC as a software is also possible. It is easy to access by specifying IP address and port via the Paho library. It comes without basic security measures;
- *IBM Watson IoT Platform*: a cloud-hosted broker. It requires more access parameters compared to test.mosquitto.org. It has embedded encryption features;

It is possible to secure the connection to test.mosquitto.org either by a TLS certificate or via a Virtual Private Network (VPN) service (ngrok, in our case). Since the on-board vehicle control logic operates at 10 Hz, we used the same rate in the message exchange between the smart RSU and the CAV.

FIGURE 13. IMB Watson IoT Platform results for a 2-device scenario and QoS levels 0 (red), 1 (green), and 2 (blue). (a) Latency values. (b) Average latency trend. (c) Standard deviation of latency. (d) CDF of latency values.

FIGURE 14. Vehicle paths. (a) Test 1. (b) Test 2.

Recalling the scheme in Fig. 3(b), which is the most realistic setting for a V2X scenario, we present detailed results in Fig. 13 where the MQTT broker is the IBM Watson IoT Platform with encrypted communication. Fig. 13(a) shows the latency values computed as RTT, while Fig. 13(b) represents their averaged trend, for three different QoS levels. Overall, the maximum latency is well below the 600 ms threshold. The standard deviations are shown in Fig. 13(c), while Fig. 13(d) summarizes the distribution of latency values in terms of Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF). It is interesting to notice the impact of the QoS: QoS level 1 is the best compromise between a low-latency low-reliability (QoS level 0) and a high-latency high-reliability (QoS level 2) communication link. Since it also provides the best stability, IBM Watson IoT Platform is the consequential choice as our communication enabler of the V2X architecture.

FIGURE 15. HMI for three different conditions from the driver's point-of-view during a demonstration. (a) VRU detected by the RSU even though not visible to the driver before the turn. Vehicle speed is 2.02 m/s, visual warning is green, TTR is 7.54 s, distance to collision is 14.47 m. (b) TTR exceeds TTC_1 , vehicle speed is 2.03 m/s (7.31 km/h), visual warning is amber, TTR is 2.27 s, distance to collision is 4.6 m. (c) TTR exceeds TTC_2 , vehicle speed is 0.15 m/s, visual warning is red, TTR is 0.84 s, distance to collision is 0.86 m, the brake has been applied autonomously and the pedestrian is safe.

Summary results on V2X latency are provided in Table 2, which facilitates the identification of the best combinations useful for our use case scenario. The use of a VPN is unfeasible as it leads to an average latency above 600 ms, while test.mosquitto.org (484.3 ms on average) and IBM Watson IoT Platform (48.83 ms on average) both satisfy the 600 ms constraint. Although an Ethernet cable plugged to the connection provider is difficult to use in a real environment, the results are useful to compare the two types

TABLE 3. Braking and safety distance: AEB tests.

Test	Velocity @trigger [km/h]	TTC TTC_2 [s]	Total braking estimated [m]	Braking ideal [m]	Min. safe ideal [m]	Min. safe real [m]	Safety real [m]	Total braking real [m]
Test 1	13.9	1.34	5.17	1.2	2.5	2.76	2.6	5.36
Test 2	19.2	1.32	7.04	2.4	4.1	4.15	3	7.15

FIGURE 16. Velocity and acceleration profiles for the tests. (a) Test 1. (b) Test 2. The reference velocity and acceleration profiles are shown by the blue and the red dashed lines. The delay of 0.33 s in braking due to brake clearance and dynamics of the hydraulic actuator clearly visible.

of connection and to assess the impact of the architecture quality: the average latency is lower (as expected) except for the test.mosquito.org broker. This can be explained considering that it is publicly available, so with congestion levels subject to high fluctuations during the day.

C. ON-BOARD VEHICLE AEB ALGORITHM

Fig. 14 shows the vehicle trajectories during the tests. The figure also shows the position of the stationary VRU (red) that has been fixed in the lane along which the vehicle is moving. This is to make sure that the VRU falls in the critical zone and that the AEB would eventually be triggered. During experimental tests, the CWAS algorithm was modified to provide an $a_{req} = -6 \text{ m/s}^2$ on braking for all speeds in order to obtain velocity profiles easier to be analyzed. The updated values of TTC_2 for the vehicle velocity for the AEB trigger have also been reported in Table 3. TTC_1 was set to 10 seconds to give the driver sufficient time to notice the alert regarding the detection of a VRU at the intersection. The warning related to the presence of the VRU at the crossing was relayed via the HMI to the driver in a staggered form from green to amber to red. Green indicates when the TTR is in safe zone and the driver does not need to reduce the velocity of the vehicle to ensure safety of VRU (Fig. 15(a)). Amber is relayed to the on-board screen in front of the driver when the TTR is in the warning zone between TTC_1 and TTC_2 , wherein the driver can react and brake accordingly on his own without the AEB taking over (Fig. 15(b)). As soon as the TTC is in the danger zone, depicted by red warning light on the HMI screen, the AEB is triggered forcing the vehicle to come to a stop to safeguard the VRU (Fig. 15(c)).

The velocity profile of the vehicle observed during the tests are shown in Fig. 16. Two tests have been presented to demonstrate the repeatability of the AEB characteristics. For the purpose of the test, the vehicles start at rest and accelerate till the TTR reaches TTC_2 when the brake is triggered. The signal states for the HMI and the AEB trigger have also been presented and a communication delay of 0.1 s can be seen between the change of state of the warning state and the transmission of the AEB trigger signal. The slopes of the ideal and measured velocity curves correspond to the acceleration value provided during the brake actuation (-6 m/s^2) which can be observed in the reference and calculated acceleration curves in red. The brake actuator response time is calculated from the ideal velocity curve at the triggering of the AEB and the imposed ideal velocity curve fits onto the measured data. This delay is found to be 0.33 s and could be ascribed to the rise time of the hydraulic component dynamics and the time taken to overcome the brake pedal clearance. A comparison between the estimated total braking distance and the measured total braking distance is reported in Table 3. In both the tests, the total braking distances, i.e., the distance between the vehicle and the stationary VRU at the start of braking, are equivalent to each other. However, the difference lies amongst the constituent distances. While the total braking distance considered a safety distance of 2 m in both cases, the measured safety distances are longer. This difference may be attributed to the overestimation of the parameters used to calculate the actuator response distance for TTC calculation since the actual braking distance could not be lower than the reported ideal values. The “real” values in the table have been acquired using the RTK-corrected GNSS sensor

whereas the “ideal” ones are calculated using the kinematic relations.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we designed, developed, and assessed a C-ITS architecture for VRU protection in an urban environment. We considered the entirety of the system in its sensing, localization, communication, and actuation phases. We differentiate our work from others by providing pedestrian-specific parameters extracted by ML algorithms for CV, and an automated way to trigger an AEB based on such parameters sent/received by a 5G V2X link. We experimentally demonstrate the use case of a CAV avoiding a collision with a VRU by means of 5G connectivity, analyzing the system parameters that allow a safe operation. This refers to the analysis of the latency of the solution, both regarding the V2X link and the braking system.

From Table 2, the two brokers satisfying the maximum latency given by the 600 ms threshold are test.mosquitto.org (average latency of 484.3 ms) and IBM Watson IoT Platform (average latency of 48.84 ms). Setting up the connection to the former is straightforward: a Python software with the broker hostname (i.e., test.mosquitto.org), the network port (i.e., 1883) and a string as pub/sub topic; by default the connection is not secured, thus TLS certificate and specific network port (i.e., 8883) must be provided manually. Connection to the latter requires a little bit more attention: hostname and network port are still needed, but now subscription topics have a different format from the publish ones because specific IDs and strings differentiate the payload and its parsing; however, here there is no unsecured connection since setup relies on TLS certificate. Different combinations of broker/QoS levels lead to heterogeneous results: an extremely reliable communication channel comes at the expense of a high latency ($QoS = 2$), whereas a fast message delivery can face an unreliable channel ($QoS = 0$). We chose the final configuration as tradeoff between these two metrics: IBM Watson IoT Platform with $QoS = 1$ as V2X communication enabler gives the lowest average latency, a maximum latency compliant with the 600 ms benchmark, and a stable V2X channel.

Concerning the localization and tracking algorithm, the obtained results highlight the important trade-off of accuracy versus latency. Prioritizing the accuracy choosing a YOLOv4 model will provide an RMSE on VRU positioning below 15 cm, and an overall latency for both detection and tracking below the 100 ms threshold for real-time operation. On the other hand, the prioritization of latency and lightness of the system by choosing the compact YOLOv4-tiny model degrades the localization performance (the RMSE increases to 24 cm), but it reduces the average latency to 20 ms.

From a control point of view, the experimental results show how the designed system works correctly and is capable of taking advantage of the timely detection of the obscured VRU at the intersection to provide a safety warning and emergency braking, avoid a collision. They also highlight the

delay and modeling errors of the vehicle hydraulic system, but this aspect did not compromise the success of the tests. The algorithm was able to maintain a safe stopping distance range by correctly accounting for the different in-vehicle delays, which have been calculated to be less than 0.5 s. The designed system provides the required braking safety while avoiding triggering of the AEB when not completely necessary, increasing the user fidelity in the system.

Future works can address how challenging situations (e.g., poor lighting conditions or 3D localization/depth estimation) impact the camera’s ability to detect VRUs. Although cameras provide valuable data for detecting VRUs, they have limitations in poor lighting conditions and depth estimation. Overcoming these challenges requires a combination of strategies, such as integrating stereo vision systems, or leveraging Deep Learning (DL) for depth estimation. Another future development can explore the integration of additional sensors, such as LiDAR and radar, in our system since they significantly enhances VRU detection. The use of sensor fusion techniques, as well as hybrid ones, overcomes the individual shortcomings of each sensor, leading to a more reliable and robust detection system that can accurately track and localize VRUs in a variety of real-world scenarios. Regarding the communication part, a possible extension can explore the usage of the DSRC technology to transmit warning messages. This can provide a detailed comparison between the cellular case (our scenario) and the WiFi case, allowing us to gather further insights on the performances of the two technologies.

In the current work, operation design domain scenario of slow moving VRUs has been considered where the irregularities of the movement range are compensated by the updated information from the RSU communication. Further investigation needs to be performed for the scenarios where the VRU moves at a significant speed to cover the predefined safety distance between the updates of the VRU position from the RSU. For these edge case scenarios of relatively faster VRUs like bicycles and other micro-mobility vehicles moving along the road-center, trajectory prediction model for the VRUs would be incorporated in the algorithm for TTC calculation.

APPENDIX

At the time of RSU installation, a calibration step is required for a correct functionality of the algorithm. During this phase the user is requested to provide the following inputs:

- (u, v) coordinates of the four corners of the ROI in the camera image space, A, B, C and D in Fig. 2 (left);
- Width of the ROI in the camera image space, in pixels W_{pixel} (e.g., 1920);
- Width of the ROI in meters W_{meters} in the real scenario;
- FPS at which the camera is working;
- LLA coordinates $\mathbf{P}_{\text{ref}}^{\text{LLA}}$ of the top-left corner of the ROI ($\mathbf{P}_{\text{ref}}^{\text{Loc}}$ in Fig. 2). These are used as reference coordinates to convert positions from local ground coordinates (x, y) into global coordinates.

Let us consider the 2D camera image space, defined by the pixel indices (u, v) , whose origin $\mathbf{O} = [u_0 \ v_0] = [0 \ 0]$ coincides with the top-left corner of the image from the camera feed. For each frame f , the VRU detection and tracking algorithm returns a set of N_{BB} detected BBs. Each BB is represented by a six-dimensional vector $\mathbf{s}^{(i)} = [u_{\text{TL}}^{(i)} \ v_{\text{TL}}^{(i)} \ u_{\text{BR}}^{(i)} \ v_{\text{BR}}^{(i)} \ v_u^{(i)} \ v_v^{(i)}]$, with $u_{\text{TL}}^{(i)}, v_{\text{TL}}^{(i)}$ being the camera image coordinates of the top-left corner of the BB, $u_{\text{BR}}^{(i)}, v_{\text{BR}}^{(i)}$ the camera image coordinates of the bottom-right corner of the BB and $v_u^{(i)}, v_v^{(i)}$ the components of BB velocity on the u and v axes, respectively. From $\mathbf{s}^{(i)}$, the centroid $\mathbf{C}^{(i)} = [C_u^{(i)} \ C_v^{(i)}]$ of the i -th BB is computed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C}^{(i)} &= \begin{bmatrix} C_u^{(i)} \\ C_v^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \left[\text{int} \left(\frac{u_{\text{TL}}^{(i)} + u_{\text{BR}}^{(i)}}{2} \right) \ \text{int} \left(\frac{v_{\text{TL}}^{(i)} + v_{\text{BR}}^{(i)}}{2} \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1})$$

Note that the coordinates $C_u^{(i)}$ and $C_v^{(i)}$ are approximated to the closest integer due to the integer characteristics of pixel in the image space.

It is our goal to estimate the VRU position by projecting the BB centroid in the camera image space at the base of the BB itself. We refer to the projected new point as $\mathbf{G}^{(i)} = [G_u^{(i)} \ G_v^{(i)}]$ as *ground point*, having the following coordinates

$$G_u^{(i)} = C_u^{(i)}, \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$G_v^{(i)} = C_v^{(i)} - \left(\frac{v_{\text{BR}}^{(i)} - v_{\text{TL}}^{(i)}}{2} \right). \quad (\text{A3})$$

Notice that the ground point $\mathbf{G}^{(i)}$ still refers to the camera image space (u, v) . To find the corresponding absolute value in the global reference, a BEV transformation is applied, which allows the conversion from the camera image space (u, v) to the ground image space (x, y) . As depicted in Fig. 2, in the projected space the image coordinates correspond to the horizontal plane coordinates whose origin coincides with the top left corner of the projected image. This operation requires the BEV algorithm to be initialized with the selected ROI in the calibration phase. By taking as input the corner points of the ROI in the camera image space, the BEV algorithm returns a 3×3 homography matrix \mathbf{M} defined as

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & b_1 \\ a_3 & a_4 & b_2 \\ c_1 & c_2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A4})$$

where a_1, a_2, a_3 and a_4 define the image transformations such as rotation and scaling, b_1 and b_2 define the translation vector and finally c_1 and c_2 define the projection vector [60]. Matrix \mathbf{M} allows for the projection of any point within the ROI from the camera image space into the ground image space. Hence, the ground coordinates of the VRU ground point $\mathbf{G}^{(i)}$ are calculated by multiplying the ground points coordinates in the camera image space by the matrix \mathbf{M} as

$$\begin{bmatrix} G_x^{(i)} \\ G_y^{(i)} \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & b_1 \\ a_3 & a_4 & b_2 \\ c_1 & c_2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} G_u \\ G_v \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A5})$$

with γ the scaling factor (output of the BEV algorithm). The VRU position in the ground image coordinates is then computed as

$$\mathbf{P}_{\text{VRU}}^{(i), \text{Loc}} = \gamma^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} G_x^{(i)} \\ G_y^{(i)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A6})$$

The last operation is the conversion of $\mathbf{P}_{\text{VRU}}^{(i), \text{Loc}}$ in LLA coordinates. To do so, a double conversion from LLA to Earth-Centered Earth-Fixed (ECEF), and back, is employed. In particular, the algorithm first converts the LLA coordinates of the reference point $\mathbf{P}_{\text{ref}}^{\text{LLA}}$ from LLA to ECEF, obtaining $\mathbf{P}_{\text{ref}}^{\text{ECEF}} = [P_{x, \text{ref}}^{\text{ECEF}} \ P_{y, \text{ref}}^{\text{ECEF}}]$. This is performed considering the WGS84 ellipsoid definition for the ECEF coordinate system. Then, since in local ground image coordinates $\mathbf{P}_{\text{ref}}^{\text{LLA}}$ corresponds to the origin of the ground image, hence $\mathbf{P}_{\text{ref}}^{\text{Loc}} = [0 \ 0]$, we can find the ECEF coordinates of each i -th VRU as

$$\mathbf{P}_{\text{VRU}}^{(i), \text{ECEF}} = \begin{bmatrix} P_{x, \text{VRU}}^{(i), \text{Loc}} + P_{x, \text{ref}}^{\text{ECEF}} & P_{y, \text{VRU}}^{(i), \text{Loc}} + P_{y, \text{ref}}^{\text{ECEF}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A7})$$

Lastly, the LLA coordinates $\mathbf{P}_{\text{VRU}}^{\text{LLA}}$ of tracked BBs are obtained by applying a conversion from the ECEF ones. Since we are only interested on the horizontal position of the detected VRUs, their altitudes is set equal to the one of $\mathbf{P}_{\text{ref}}^{\text{LLA}}$.

Besides the LLA coordinates of each BB, the algorithm also returns an estimate of its speed $v_{\text{VRU}}^{(i)}$ and direction $\theta_{\text{VRU}}^{(i)}$. Note that the speed $v_{\text{VRU}}^{(i)}$ is measured in m/s, and it is obtained upon conversion from a velocity estimate $v_{\text{VRU}}^{(i)} = [v_u^{(i)} \ v_v^{(i)}]$ in the camera frame, measured in pixels/s. This implies the following relationship

$$v_{\text{VRU}}^{(i)} = v_{\text{VRU}}^{(i)} \cdot \frac{W_{\text{meters}}}{W_{\text{pixel}}} \quad [\text{m/s}], \quad (\text{A8})$$

where the scaling factors W_{pixel} and W_{meters} account for the width of the ROI in pixels and meters, respectively. The velocities in local coordinates $v_u^{(i)}$ and $v_v^{(i)}$ are also used to estimate the motion direction of the i -th VRU as

$$\theta_{\text{VRU}}^{(i)} = \arctan \left(-\frac{v_v^{(i)}}{v_u^{(i)}} \right). \quad (\text{A9})$$

For each inference frame f , the algorithm returns a *pickle* file containing all the estimated information regarding the N_{BB} tracked BBs: their estimated position in LLA coordinates, speed, direction and the ID assigned by the tracking algorithm. This file is then sent to the CAV over the implemented 5G V2X communication system.

REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Yuan et al., "Cross-domain resource orchestration for the edge-computing-enabled smart road," *IEEE Netw.*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 60–67, Sep./Oct. 2020.
- [2] T. D. Borba, O. Vaculín, H. Marzbani, and R. N. Jazar, "Increasing safety of automated driving by infrastructure-based sensors," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 94974–94991, 2023.
- [3] M. Kiraz, F. Sivrikaya, and S. Albayrak, "A survey on sensor selection and placement for connected and automated mobility," *IEEE Open J. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 5, pp. 692–710, 2024.

- [4] L. Zhu, F. R. Yu, Y. Wang, B. Ning, and T. Tang, "Big data analytics in intelligent transportation systems: A survey," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 383–398, Jan. 2019.
- [5] S.-Y. Lin, C.-M. Huang, and T.-Y. Wu, "Multi-access edge computing-based vehicle-vehicle-RSU data offloading over the multi-RSU-overlapped environment," *IEEE Open J. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 3, pp. 7–32, 2022.
- [6] M. H. C. Garcia et al., "A tutorial on 5G NR V2X communications," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1972–2026, 3rd Quart., 2021.
- [7] J. Clancy et al., "Wireless access for V2X communications: Research, challenges and opportunities," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 2082–2119, 3rd Quart., 2024.
- [8] C.-X. Wang et al., "On the road to 6G: Visions, requirements, key technologies, and testbeds," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 905–974, 2nd Quart., 2023.
- [9] J. Choi, V. Marojevic, C. B. Dietrich, J. H. Reed, and S. Ahn, "Survey of spectrum regulation for intelligent transportation systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 140145–140160, 2020.
- [10] (FCC, Washington, DC, USA). *Amendment of the Commission's Rules Regarding Dedicated Short-Range Communication Services in the 5.850-5.925 GHz Band (5.9 GHz Band)*. Accessed: Apr. 1, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.fcc.gov/public/attachments/FCC-02-302A1.pdf>
- [11] V. Maglogiannis, D. Naudts, S. Hadiwardoyo, D. van den Akker, J. Marquez-Barja, and I. Moerman, "Experimental V2X evaluation for C-V2X and ITS-G5 technologies in a real-life highway environment," *IEEE Trans. Netw. Service Manag.*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 1521–1538, Jun. 2022.
- [12] P. Li, K. Wu, Y. Cheng, S. T. Parker, and D. A. Noyce, "How does C-V2X perform in urban environments? Results from real-world experiments on urban arterials," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Veh.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 2520–2530, Jan. 2024.
- [13] L. Italiano, B. Camajori Tedeschini, M. Brambilla, H. Huang, M. Nicoli, and H. Wymeersch, "A tutorial on 5G positioning," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, early access, Aug. 23, 2024, doi: [10.1109/COMST.2024.3449031](https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2024.3449031).
- [14] M. Brambilla et al., "Integration of 5G and GNSS technologies for enhanced positioning: An experimental study," *IEEE Open J. Commun. Soc.*, vol. 5, pp. 7197–7215, 2024.
- [15] B. Camajori Tedeschini et al., "A feasibility study of 5G positioning with current cellular network deployment," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2023, Art. no. 15281.
- [16] (5GAA, Munich, Germany). *Study of Spectrum Needs for Safety Related Intelligent Transportation Systems—Day 1 and Advanced use Cases*. Accessed: Apr. 1, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://5gaa.org/content/uploads/2021/10/5GAA_Day1_and_adv_Use_Cases_Spectrum_Needs_Study_V2.0.pdf
- [17] R. Viterbo et al., "Evaluating the V2X latency for vehicle positioning: A comparison between 5G-V2X and ITS-G5," in *Proc. IEEE 8th Forum Res. Technol. Soc. Ind. Innov. (RTSI)*, 2024, pp. 271–276.
- [18] G. Mao, Y. Hui, X. Ren, C. Li, and Y. Shao, "The Internet of Things for smart roads: A road map from present to future road infrastructure," *IEEE Intell. Transp. Syst. Mag.*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 66–76, Nov./Dec. 2022.
- [19] E. Thonhofer et al., "Infrastructure-based digital twins for cooperative, connected, automated driving and smart road services," *IEEE Open J. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 4, pp. 311–324, 2023.
- [20] B. Lv et al., "LiDAR-enhanced connected infrastructures sensing and broadcasting high-resolution traffic information serving smart cities," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 79895–79907, 2019.
- [21] L. Barbieri, B. Camajori Tedeschini, M. Brambilla, and M. Nicoli, "Deep learning-based cooperative LiDAR sensing for improved vehicle positioning," *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.*, vol. 72, pp. 1666–1682, Mar. 2024.
- [22] B. Camajori Tedeschini, M. Brambilla, L. Barbieri, G. Balducci, and M. Nicoli, "Cooperative Lidar sensing for pedestrian detection: Data association based on message passing neural networks," *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.*, vol. 71, pp. 3028–3042, Aug. 2023.
- [23] E. Arnold, M. Dianati, R. de Temple, and S. Fallah, "Cooperative perception for 3D object detection in driving scenarios using infrastructure sensors," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1852–1864, Mar. 2022.
- [24] G. Thandavarayan, M. Sepulcre, and J. Gozalvez, "Cooperative perception for connected and automated vehicles: Evaluation and impact of congestion control," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 197665–197683, 2020.
- [25] H. Lee, H. K. Kim, S. H. Oh, and S. H. Lee, "Machine learning-aided cooperative localization under a dense urban environment: Demonstrates universal feasibility," *IEEE Veh. Technol. Mag.*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 78–89, Sep. 2024.
- [26] B. Häfner, V. Bajpai, J. Ott, and G. A. Schmitt, "A survey on cooperative architectures and maneuvers for connected and automated vehicles," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 380–403, 1st Quart., 2022.
- [27] N. Goulet and B. Ayalew, "Distributed maneuver planning with connected and automated vehicles for boosting traffic efficiency," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 10887–10901, Aug. 2022.
- [28] G. Ciaramitaro, M. Brambilla, M. Nicoli, and U. Spagnolini, "Signalling design in sensor-assisted mmWave communications for cooperative driving," *IEEE Open J. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 4, pp. 493–505, 2023.
- [29] D. Tagliaferri, M. Brambilla, M. Nicoli, and U. Spagnolini, "Sensor-aided beamwidth and power control for next generation vehicular communications," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 56301–56317, 2021.
- [30] C. Perfecto, J. Del Ser, and M. Bennis, "Millimeter-wave V2V communications: Distributed association and beam alignment," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 35, no. 9, pp. 2148–2162, Sep. 2017.
- [31] S. Liu, L. Liu, J. Tang, B. Yu, Y. Wang, and W. Shi, "Edge computing for autonomous driving: Opportunities and challenges," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 107, no. 8, pp. 1697–1716, Aug. 2019.
- [32] J. Zhang and K. B. Letaief, "Mobile edge intelligence and computing for the Internet of Vehicles," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 108, no. 2, pp. 246–261, Feb. 2020.
- [33] S. R. Pokhrel, N. Kumar, and A. Walid, "Towards ultra reliable low latency multipath TCP for connected autonomous vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 70, no. 8, pp. 8175–8185, Aug. 2021.
- [34] A. Mostafizi, C. Koll, and H. Wang, "A decentralized and coordinated routing algorithm for connected and autonomous vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 11505–11517, Aug. 2022.
- [35] F. Karagulian, C. Liberto, M. Corazza, G. Valenti, A. Dumitru, and M. Nigro, "Pedestrian flows characterization and estimation with computer vision techniques," *Urban Sci.*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 65, 2023.
- [36] Z. Zou, K. Chen, Z. Shi, Y. Guo, and J. Ye, "Object detection in 20 years: A survey," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 111, no. 3, pp. 257–276, Mar. 2023.
- [37] M. R. Bachute and J. M. Subhedar, "Autonomous driving architectures: Insights of machine learning and deep learning algorithms," *Mach. Learn. Appl.*, vol. 6, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 100164.
- [38] R. Girshick, J. Donahue, T. Darrell, and J. Malik, "Region-based convolutional networks for accurate object detection and segmentation," *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 142–158, Jan. 2016.
- [39] C. Szegedy et al., "Going deeper with convolutions," 2014, *arXiv:1409.4842*.
- [40] D. Tomè, F. Monti, L. Baroffio, L. Bondi, M. Tagliasacchi, and S. Tubaro, "Deep convolutional neural networks for pedestrian detection," *Signal Process., Image Commun.*, vol. 47, pp. 482–489, Sep. 2016.
- [41] R. Giuliano, F. Mazzenga, E. Innocenti, F. Fallucchi, and I. Habib, "Communication network architectures for driver assistance systems," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 20, p. 6867, 2021.
- [42] S. K. Maurya and A. Choudhary, "Pedestrian detection and vulnerability decision in videos," in *Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. Adv. Comput. Commun. Paradigms (ICACCP)*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [43] Y. Zhuang, Z. Pu, J. Hu, and Y. Wang, "Illumination and temperature-aware multispectral networks for edge-computing-enabled pedestrian detection," *IEEE Trans. Netw. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1282–1295, May/Jun. 2022.
- [44] P. Rito et al., "Aveiro tech city living lab: A communication, sensing, and computing platform for city environments," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 10, no. 15, pp. 13489–13510, Aug. 2023.
- [45] P. Teixeira, S. Sargento, P. Rito, M. Luís, and F. Castro, "A sensing, communication and computing approach for vulnerable road users safety," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 4914–4930, 2023.

- [46] D. Vignarca, M. Vignati, S. Arrigoni, and E. Sabbioni, "Infrastructure-based vehicle localization through camera calibration for I2V communication warning," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 16, p. 7136, 2023.
- [47] "Advanced driver assistance systems market size USD 158.64 Bn by 2032." Precedence Research. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/advanced-driver-assistance-systems-market>
- [48] L. Masello, G. Castignani, B. Sheehan, F. Murphy, and K. McDonnell, "On the road safety benefits of advanced driver assistance systems in different driving contexts," *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.*, vol. 15, Sep. 2022, Art. no. 100670.
- [49] D. Stewart, C. J. Cudworth, and J. Lishman, "Misperception of time-to-collision by drivers in pedestrian accidents," *Perception*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 1227–1244, 1993.
- [50] Y. Zhang, A. Carballo, H. Yang, and K. Takeda, "Perception and sensing for autonomous vehicles under adverse weather conditions: A survey," *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, vol. 196, pp. 146–177, Feb. 2023.
- [51] M. Khayyat, S. Arrigoni, and F. Cheli, "Development and simulation-based testing of a 5G-connected intersection AEB system," *Veh. Syst. Dyn.*, vol. 60, no. 12, pp. 4059–4078, 2022.
- [52] M. Baek, H. Lee, H. Choi, and K. Ko, "Development of intersection collision avoidance algorithm for B2V safety service," *Int. J. Control Autom.*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 229–240, 2015.
- [53] S. Y. Gelbal, S. Arslan, H. Wang, B. Aksun-Guvenc, and L. Guvenc, "Elastic band based pedestrian collision avoidance using V2X communication," in *Proc. IEEE Intell. Veh. Symp. (IV)*, 2017, pp. 270–276.
- [54] J. Kotte, C. Schmeichel, A. Zlocki, H. Gathmann, and L. Eckstein, "Concept of an enhanced V2X pedestrian collision avoidance system with a cost function-based pedestrian model," *Traffic Injury Prev.*, vol. 18, pp. S37–S43, Apr. 2017.
- [55] R. Matsumi, P. Raksincharoensak, and M. Nagai, "Autonomous braking control system for pedestrian collision avoidance by using potential field," *IFAC Proc. Vol.*, vol. 46, no. 21, pp. 328–334, 2013.
- [56] G. Xiog, T. Yang, M. Li, Y. Zhang, W. Song, and J. Gong, "A novel V2X-based pedestrian collision avoidance system and the effects analysis of communication delay and packet loss on its application," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Veh. Electron. Saf. (ICVES)*, 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [57] "Intelligent transport system (ITS); vehicular communications; basic set of applications; collective perception service; release 2," ETSI, Sophia Antipolis, France, document 103 324, 2023.
- [58] A. Bochkovskiy, C.-Y. Wang, and H.-Y. M. Liao, "YOLOv4: Optimal speed and accuracy of object detection," 2020, *arXiv:2004.10934*.
- [59] N. Wojke, A. Bewley, and D. Paulus, "Simple online and realtime tracking with a deep association metric," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Image Process. (ICIP)*, 2017, pp. 3645–3649.
- [60] R. Hartley and A. Zisserman, *Multiple View Geometry in Computer Vision*, 2nd ed. New York, NY, USA: Cambridge Univ. Press, 2003.
- [61] "Paho python client." Accessed: Apr. 1, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://eclipse.dev/paho/index.php?page=clients/python/index.php>
- [62] "ROS—Robot operating system." Accessed: Apr. 1, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ros.org/>
- [63] M. Bersani, M. Vignati, S. Mentasti, S. Arrigoni, and F. Cheli, "Vehicle state estimation based on Kalman filters," in *Proc. AEIT Int. Conf. Electr. Electron. Technol. Automot. (AEIT AUTOMOTIVE)*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [64] D. Vignarca, S. Arrigoni, M. Vignati, and E. Sabbioni, "Analysis of communication delays in roadside detection systems for cooperative AEB implementation," in *Proc. IEEE Veh. Power Propulsion Conf. (VPPC)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [65] S. Arrigoni, S. Mentasti, F. Cheli, M. Matteucci, and F. Braghin, "Design of a prototypical platform for autonomous and connected vehicles," in *Proc. AEIT Int. Conf. Electr. Electron. Technol. Automot. (AEIT AUTOMOTIVE)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [66] J. Lee and K.-i. Hwang, "YOLO with adaptive frame control for real-time object detection applications," *Multimedia Tools Appl.*, vol. 81, no. 25, pp. 36375–36396, 2022.
- [67] G. Jocher and J. Qiu. "Ultralytics YOLO11." 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>
- [68] B. Wolfe, B. Seppelt, B. Mehler, B. Reimer, and R. Rosenholtz, "Rapid holistic perception and evasion of road hazards," *J. Exp. Psychol., General*, vol. 149, no. 3, p. 490, 2020.
- [69] M. Green, "How long does it take to stop? Methodological analysis of driver perception-brake times," *Transp. Human Factors*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 195–216, 2000.